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COMPARISON OF Tc-99m-MIBI PARATHYROID SCINTIGRAPHY FINDINGS AND BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS IN PATIENTS WITH PRIMARY AND TERTIARY HYPERPARATHYROIDISM

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Background and objectives: Tc-99m-MIBI scintigraphy is used for preoperative localization of parathyroid adenoma based on increased tracer uptake in hyper functioning parathyroid tissue. The aim of this study was to compare the levels of parathyroid hormone (PTH), calcium, phosphor, crosslaps and osteocalcin with results of Tc-99m-MIBI parathyroid scintigraphy in patients with primary and tertiary hyperparathyroidism and to determine significance of Tc-99m-MIBI scintigraphy in tertiary hyperparathyroidism.

Methods: Fifty four patients with MIBI positive findings on Tc-99m-MIBI dual phase (early and late imaging) scintigraphy, verified by postoperative patohistological analysis were included in study. Ten patients had tertiary hyperparathyroidism and 44 patients had primary hyperparathyroidism. Patients with tertiary hyperparathyroidism underwent kidney transplantation 6 to 24 months prior to Tc-99m-MIBI scintigraphy, and had preserved renal function.

Results: All of the patients included in the study had elevated PTH levels ranging from 70 to 1447 ng/l. Average value of PTH level in primary hyperparathyroidism group was 352 ng/l, and in tertiary hyperparathyroidism group 296 ng/l. In both of the groups elevated calcium levels were detected, but without statistically significant difference (2,69 mmol/l in primary and 2,78 mmol/l in tertiary hyperparathyroidism). Serum levels of phosphor were lower in both groups in range from 0,44 to 1,04 mmol/l with average value 0,77 mmol/l in group of primary hyperparathyroidism and 0,75 mmol/l in group of tertiary hyperparathyroidism. Crosslaps was elevated in both groups (1578 pg/ml in primary and 1460 pg/ml in tertiary hyperparathyroidism), as well as osteocalcin levels (79 ng/ml in primary and 82 ng/ml in tertiary hyperparathyroidism).

Conclusion: In patients with primary and tertiary hyperparathyroidism differences in biochemical findings were not statistically significant, despite the preexisting renal failure and disturbed bone metabolism in patients with tertiary hyperparathyroidism.

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